

Sri Ramakrishna Paramahansa: An Inspiration for the mission of Women Empowerment

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Abstract : Women Empowerment is a process of initiative taken by policy framers, educationist, government and other bodies to provide equitable opportunities in every aspects of development like education, health, governance, employment etc to women. The real operational definition of women empowerment is *accepting and allowing* the people (women) who are outside of the decision making process. Law, Judiciary, reservation system as the mechanism of safeguard and upliftment will be futile if the other section of society does not accept the dignity or worth of women. Sri Ramakrishna Paramahansa was the man of example who has shown the path, the way the women should be respected and responded by the male dominated society.

“The Ramakrishna Mission stands for the mission of Sri Ramakrishna on earth.” Swami Bhuteshananda, the 12th President of the Ramakrishna Order, appraised rightly the Ramakrishna Mission in this manner. If we want to review the endeavours of Ramakrishna Mission and Ramakrishna Sarada Mission regarding women empowerment, we must initially assimilate the vibrant message of Sri Ramakrishna (1836–1886). It is remarkable that he was not a social reformer yet “He was the saviour of women, saviour of the masses, saviour of all high and low”¹, said Swami Vivekananda. (It was written to Swami Ramakrishnananda from the West in 1895.) In nineteenth century, he was the person, who with his unique vision and wisdom expressed the suppression and distress of women as the root of India’s degeneration.

When the mental set-up of the orthodox Hindus were not favourable to accept the intellect and prudence of women, Sri Ramakrishna received the spiritual guidance of a nun with immense spiritual power, named Bhairavi Brahmani, in 1861.

His attitude towards his wife Sri Sarada Devi was also significant. One day while massaging his feet, Sri Sarada Devi wanted to know about his husband’s view regarding herself. An amazing answer came from her husband, “The same Mother that is in the (Kali) temple, gave birth to this body and now lives at the music tower (His own mother Chandramani Devi was then living there), and she, again, is stroking my feet at the present moment.” It was not a mere statement, but honestly, Sri Ramakrishna proved it by worshiping his eighteen years old wife as the Mother of the universe on the new-moon night of 5th June 1872 (Shodashi puja). He offered all the fruits of his spiritual attainments at her feet along with his rosary.

Though they both absorbed into transcendental bliss in their married life, some intellectuals (Pratap Chandra Majumder, Sumit Sarkar etc.) criticises Sri Ramakrishna as misogynist and sexually diseased person. Brahma leader Pratap Chandra Majumder, the former admirer of Sri Ramakrishna, wrote a letter (1895) to Professor Max Muller condemning Sri Ramakrishna’s ‘barbarous’ attitude towards Sri Sarada Devi, as if he compelled her to maintain celibacy in their wedded life. Professor Max Muller refuted Mr Majumder’s allegation with the help of a letter of Mrs Sara Bull, who met Sri Sarada Devi and came to know her revering feelings for her husband. Here we must consider the writings (‘My Master’) of Swami Vivekananda, where he described his Master’s attitude in this regard. “When as a temple priest his extraordinary worship made people think him deranged in his head, his relatives tried to back him to home and married him to a little girl, thinking that that would turn his thoughts and restore the balance of his mind. Although he came back but merged himself deeper in his madness as we see. Sometimes, in our country, boys are married as children and have no voice in the matter; their parents marry them. Of course such a marriage is little more than a formal engagement of marriage. When they are married they still continue to live their parents, and the real marriage takes place when the wife grows older, when it is customary for the husband to bring back his bride to his own home. In this case, however, the husband had entirely forgotten that he had a wife. In her far off home the girl had heard that her husband had become a religious enthusiast, and many people think him that he was mentally ill. She resolved to learn the truth for herself, so she set out and walked to the place where her husband was. When at last she stood in her husband’s presence, he at once admitted her right to his life, although in India any person, may be man or woman, who embraces a spiritual life, is thereby freed from all other obligations. The young man fell at the feet of his wife and said, ‘As for me, the Mother has shown me that she resides in every woman, and so I have learnt to look upon every woman as Mother. That is one idea I can have about you; but if you wish to drag me into the world, as I have been married to you, I am at your service.’

The maiden was a pure and noble soul and was able to understand her husband’s aspirations and sympathise with them. She quickly told him that she had no wish to drag him down to a life of worldliness; but all that she desired was to remain near him, to serve him, and to learn from him. She became one of his most devoted disciples, always revering him as a divine being. Thus through his wife’s consent the last barrier was removed, and he was free to lead the life he had chosen.”²

They both decided and willingly chose the path of celibacy. Therefore, there was no question of deprivation or denial. Rather their married life was much healthier in respect of the then social propensity. In the words of Christopher Isherwood, “The Hindu practice of marriage had become degraded at that time. The wife was a mere servant of her husband’s domestic convenience and his lust. But Ramakrishna educated his wife in many ways and watched over her like a father. He did not even treat her as an equal; he worshipped her as an embodiment of the Mother.”³ Sri Ramakrishna was the genuine mentor of Sri

Sarada Devi. At the same time, he too gave proper value to her opinions, had faith on her potential, and prophesied that she would do much more good for the people than he did.

The feminists of the following times misunderstood him as he advised his male devotees to renounce woman and gold (*kamini-kanchan*) for spiritual attainment. According to the feminist outlook, he dishonoured womankind by indicating them as the impediment in the path of spiritual fervour. However, actual interpretation of his advice was to relinquish sexual desires as well as lusts of lucre are the first and foremost characteristics of austerity. These are applicable to all humankind irrespective of their gender. Whenever he met his female devotees then also he advised the same. Since nobody recorded his conversation with female folk as M (Mahendranath Gupta) had done in case of male devotees, the word *kamini-kanchan* is wrongly interpreted.

According to Sri Ramakrishna's view, all women are the part of supreme power and he gave motherly admiration to all of them without considering their caste or creed. At his age of nine, he had accepted the midwife Dhani Kamarni (blacksmith woman) as his alms-mother at the time of his *Upanayana* (thread ceremony) by receiving the first alms from her. His entire family was against his stance, as it was customary that the alms-mother must be a Brahmin woman. When the caste-consciousness was strong rooted in the Hindu society, with rigidity, the little boy tackled the situation and throughout his life, he gave Dhani the special status and respect.

His impartial blissful love oozed even upon the prostitutes and the actresses of the then theatre. At the last part of the nineteenth century, inclusion of female actors made advance the Bengali theatre. On the other hand, most of the cultured, gentle men started to show aversion towards theatre due to the participation of women who had mostly come from brothel. However, Sri Ramakrishna did not take them as mere harlot but delightful embodiment of the Divine Mother. He visited the theatre hall and enjoyed the religious plays several times with transcendental pleasure. His heart-felt blessings showered upon the famous actress (*noti*) Binodini and others. To him, mythological dramas were not the element of amusement only but also a good equipment of mass education, which would teach people a great deal. Sri Ramakrishna's liberal attitude towards Bengali theatre as well as female actors certainly transformed the mental set-up of Bengali orthodox to some extent.

If we analyse the activities and the sayings of Sri Ramakrishna we will find the keynote of the modern conception regarding emancipation of women. The then social reformers being male enjoyed the superior status in the society. With superiority complex, they felt pity for their deprived counterpart. By assuring legal protection or by establishing girls' school they tried to lend a hand for their uplift. However, Sri Ramakrishna's stance was entirely different. He was the first man who accepted the higher status of women as they were the manifestations of Supreme Power. He always taught his male disciples not to look down upon women as well as he made them understand that female folk did not deserve sympathy but sheer reverence. He earnestly instructed his female disciple Gouri Ma to do something effectual for the proper manifestation of the inherent inner strength of the women and he assured his full support to her endeavour regarding this (in Sri Ramakrishna's words – "I am pouring water, you knead the mud"). According to his view, all humankind without any distinction of gender, caste or creeds were competent for spiritual liberation and self-realization. With full regard, he gave Gouri Ma the ochre clothe recognizing her ascetic life. Such an advanced outlook in the social perspective of nineteenth century was quite amazing.

References

1. The complete Works of Swami Vivekananda, Vol. VI Advaita Ashrama, Calcutta, Mayavati Memorial Edition, Pp 335
2. The complete Works of Swami Vivekananda, Vol. IV, Advaita Ashrama, Calcutta, Mayavati Memorial Edition, Pp 172-173
3. Christopher Isherwood, Ramakrishna and his disciples, Advaita Ashrama, Calcutta, 1965, Pp 83